
AN EXPLORATORY STUDY ON POST COVID-19 CRISIS ON LEGAL EDUCATION OF PAKISTAN

Sardar Ali Shah (ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0028-7614)

Assistant Professor, Institute of Law, University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan.

Muhammad Hassan (ORCID ID: 0000-0003-3586-8590)

Lecturer, Department of Law, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Pakistan.

Raheela Bibi Syed (ORCID ID: 0009-0003-7559-0578)

Assistant Professor, Government Nazreht College, Hyderabad, Pakistan.

ABSTRACT

It is touching almost two years since the COVID-19 pandemic led to a prolonged lockdown in countries all over the world affecting various sectors including the education sector where its impact is persistent and ongoing. The online method of imparting knowledge has become a fallback option to replace the traditional face to face (F2F) method which has been used for time immemorial. The sudden shift to the online method has taken the education sector by surprise as there is a lack of adequate preparation among the key stakeholders inclusive of educators, students, and educational institutions themselves. However, it must be noted that online learning is not a totally new method as its presence has been evident in the form of blended learning adopted in the past decades. The main difference is that under blended learning, online learning was inserted in F2F learning to add diversity in the teaching and learning method but today, it has replaced face to face learning totally. This transformation has brought about numerous concerns among stakeholders specifically to those involved in legal education. Legal education had been affected significantly due to its unique characteristics that has specific outcomes including legal reading, legal writing, factual analysis and argumentation skills, whilst written and oral communication, problem-solving, information technology, teambuilding skills are included in the list of generic outcomes. Further, it requires clinical legal education, project-based method, problem-based method, moot court, role play, field trip, group work, group discussion, etc. which cannot be addressed adequately through online learning. In view of this, the current qualitative research aims to understand the challenges triggered by the new method of learning through interviews conducted via online tools such as Microsoft Teams from the various perspectives including educators, students and key representatives from the educational institutions. The research is significant as being exploratory research, it will shed light on the challenges that are in existence generating responsiveness within the stakeholders to identify the solutions by the incoming research on this issue.

Keywords: COVID-19, Legal Education, COVID-19 Crisis, Coronavirus, Pakistan.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7795816](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7795816)